

Renal Outcome at 3 Months after Acute Kidney Injury following Acute Poisoning and Envenomation

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Abstract

Background: Acute kidney injury (AKI) due to toxic exposures remains a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in Bangladesh, yet local data on its clinical spectrum, outcomes, and predictors are limited. The current study was conducted to describe the socio-demographic and clinical characteristics, patterns of toxic exposure, outcomes, and laboratory parameters of AKI following poisoning and envenomation.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted on 51 patients with toxin-induced AKI admitted to a tertiary hospital in Bangladesh. Data on demographics, clinical features, type of exposure, laboratory parameters, renal outcomes, and mortality were collected. Baseline and peak creatinine, complete blood counts, serum urea, electrolytes, liver function tests, and coagulation parameters were analyzed. Outcomes were categorized as complete renal recovery, progression to CKD, and death. Statistical analyses included Chi-square/Fisher's exact test for categorical variables and independent sample t-tests for continuous variables; $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Findings: Among 51 patients, 40 (78.4%) had poisoning and 11 (21.6%) had envenomation-related AKI. Paraquat (40%) and organophosphate compounds (15%) were the leading poisons, while wasp sting, unknown snake bite, and Russell's viper accounted for 27.3% each among envenomation. In addition, envenomation-related AKI was associated with more local tissue injury, hematuria and bleeding manifestations. Paraquat poisoning was the most lethal exposure (71% mortality). However, overall mortality was 35.3%, primarily due to respiratory failure (33.3%), followed by multiorgan dysfunction syndrome (22.2%). Mortality was higher among patients with delayed hospital presentation (62.9 ± 31.1 vs 41.3 ± 15.3 hours; $p = 0.001$), higher baseline (6.19 ± 2.37 mg/dL; $p = 0.001$) and peak creatinine (10.06 ± 2.43 mg/dL; $p = 0.045$), elevated serum urea and deranged

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hematological and liver parameters. Strong statistical association was observed between hypotension and poor outcomes ($p=0.001$). New-onset CKD occurred in 13.7%; while 47.1% achieved complete renal recovery.

Conclusion: Toxin-induced AKI in Bangladesh carries high morbidity and mortality, with paraquat poisoning and Russell's viper envenomation being particularly lethal. High baseline and peak creatinine, delayed hospital arrival, and paraquat exposure are key predictors of poor outcome. Early recognition, intensive supportive care, and public health interventions targeting toxic exposures are crucial in terms of improving outcomes.

Introduction

Acute poisoning remains a significant public health problem in many low- and middle-income countries, including Bangladesh, where it contributes notably to emergency admissions and in-hospital mortality. Studies from tertiary care centers reflect that, poisoning is among the leading causes of preventable deaths, with pesticides being particularly implicated due to their widespread agricultural use and ready availability in rural communities [1]. The burden of poisoning in Bangladesh includes ingestion of pesticides, rodenticides, plant toxins, pharmaceuticals, chemicals, alcohol adulterants such as methanol, as well as envenomation from snakes, scorpions, and insects [2]. Mortality related to pesticide poisoning is substantially higher in developing regions than in high-income countries, reflecting delayed presentation, limited access to intensive care, and inadequate regulatory control of toxic substances [3].

Acute kidney injury (AKI) is a common and potentially reversible clinical condition characterized by abrupt impairment of renal function. AKI develops over a period of seven days or less and is defined by either a $\geq 50\%$ increase in serum creatinine within one week, an increase of ≥ 0.3 mg/dL (26.5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) within 48 hours, or a reduction in urine output lasting six hours or more [4]. Even mild AKI is associated with significant morbidity, prolonged hospitalization, and increased risk of long-term chronic kidney disease (CKD) [5].

AKI secondary to poisoning involves a complex interplay of mechanisms targeting renal tubular cells, rendering them susceptible to direct and indirect toxic insults [6]. Direct nephrotoxicity may result from medications and toxins such as aminoglycosides, vancomycin, and contrast agents that disrupt mitochondrial function, often leading to acute tubular necrosis (ATN), which is classically indicated by "muddy brown casts" in the urine [7]. Other pathophysiological mechanisms include acute interstitial nephritis triggered by hypersensitivity reactions to beta-lactams, quinolones, or NSAIDs, crystal-induced AKI in the context of metabolic disturbances, and glomerular injury from agents such as bisphosphonates and hydralazine [8]. Envenomation-related AKI occurs through hemolysis, myotoxicity, capillary leak, hypotension, and coagulopathy, contributing to tubular injury and impaired renal perfusion [6].

Clinically, poisoning-related AKI manifests with a broad spectrum of signs, including dysuria, hematuria, oliguria, anuria, or systemic hypertension [6, 9]. Urine abnormalities can provide important diagnostic clues: red urine may follow hydroxocobalamin therapy for cyanide poisoning, brown urine may indicate acetaminophen overdose, black urine may result from drugs such as metronidazole, nitrofurantoin, or methocarbamol, and blue or green urine can occur with methylene blue or certain pesticide exposures [9,10]. Rarely, purple urine associated with purple urine bag syndrome reflects Gram-negative bacteriuria, while white urine may suggest severe urinary tract infection or urinary tuberculosis [11]. Laboratory evaluation, including urinalysis, toxicological screening, and measurement of serum creatinine and electrolytes, is essential for diagnosis, monitoring, and guiding therapeutic interventions [6].

Despite numerous studies addressing AKI from individual toxins or envenomation, comprehensive analyses of poisoning- and drug-induced AKI across multiple agents remain limited. For instance, in a previous Indian study, it was found that, in patients with snakebite-induced AKI, 20.7% developed AKI, with shock and thrombocytopenia predicting mortality, and nearly half of survivors experiencing adverse long-term renal outcomes [12]. Management strategies, including prompt toxin neutralization, supportive care, hydration, antidotes or antivenom administration, and renal replacement therapy, are crucial for improving outcomes and reducing long-term renal impairment [6,13].

In Bangladesh, data on the incidence, clinical characteristics, and outcomes of AKI following poisoning and envenomation are scarce. This study aims to determine the frequency, characteristics, and three-month renal outcomes of AKI in patients presenting with acute poisoning and envenomation at tertiary care hospitals, and to identify clinical factors associated with incomplete renal recovery. Understanding these patterns is essential for guiding preventive strategies and optimizing clinical management.

Method

Study Design and Setting

This was a prospective observational study conducted over an 18-month period in the Departments of

Nephrology of three tertiary care hospitals in Dhaka, Bangladesh:

1. Dhaka Medical College and Hospital,
2. Sir Salimullah Medical College & Mitford Hospital, and
3. Shaheed Suhrawardy Medical College & Hospital.

Study Population

The study included all patients aged >18 years, of either sex, admitted with a history of acute poisoning or envenomation who subsequently developed AKI. We enrolled a total of 51 patients in this study; 40 patients were in the acute poisoning group and 11 in the envenomation group.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion criteria

- Age >18 years
- AKI following acute poisoning or envenomation (defined by KDIGO 2012 criteria) ^[4]

Exclusion criteria

- Known pre-existing CKD
- Patients who did not provide informed consent

Sampling Technique

The patients were enrolled by purposive method.

Data Collection and Clinical Evaluation

Detailed history and clinical examinations were performed at admission, focusing on:

- Time from exposure to hospital arrival
- Hemodynamic status (hypotension)
- Urine output (oliguria/anuria)
- Features suggestive of CKD (to exclude chronic cases)

Baseline serum creatinine was defined as the first recorded value at presentation or the value documented from the referring facility. AKI was diagnosed based on KDIGO 2012 criteria. ^[4] Patients showing creatinine change ≥ 0.3 mg/dL during hospitalization were also classified as AKI when baseline values were uncertain.

Laboratory and Diagnostic Investigations

All patients underwent:

- Complete blood count
- Serum creatinine, urea, electrolytes
- Liver function tests (bilirubin, SGPT)
- Prothrombin time/INR
- Creatine phosphokinase (CPK) where indicated

- 20-minute whole blood clotting test (for envenomation)
- Urine routine and microscopic examination
- Chest X-ray (PA view)
- Ultrasound of whole abdomen

Serum creatinine was measured using Erba Mannheim assay. CBC was analyzed using ERMA PCE-210N automated cell counter. Other biochemical tests were processed in the respective hospital laboratories.

Management and Follow-Up

Patients were monitored daily with clinical assessment and repeated serum creatinine measurements. Hemodialysis was initiated when indicated based on standard clinical criteria. Hemoperfusion and CRRT were not available during the study period.

Patients were followed until discharge. After discharge, renal outcomes were reassessed at 3 months, categorized as:

- Resolution of AKI: eGFR ≥ 60 mL/min/1.73 m² without proteinuria or structural abnormalities
 - Progression to CKD: eGFR < 60 mL/min/1.73 m² and/or persistent proteinuria or imaging abnormalities
- eGFR was calculated using the MDRD equation.

Outcome Measures

- Duration of hospital stay
- Requirement of hemodialysis
- In-hospital mortality
- Renal recovery status at 3 months

Statistics

Data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS v. 25.0)

- Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation.
- Categorical variables were presented as frequency and percentage.
- Comparisons were performed using independent t-test or ANOVA for parametric data and Chi-square test for categorical variables.
- A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethics

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethical Review Committee of Dhaka Medical College. Informed written consent was obtained from all participants. Confidentiality and autonomy were maintained throughout the study.

Results

Table 1: Socio-Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Participants (n=51)

	Poisoning (n=40) [n/%]	Envenomation (n=11) [n/%]	p-value
Socio-demographic characteristics			
Age (in years)			
≤ 20	13 (32.5)	0 (0.0)	
21-30	16 (40.0)	3 (27.3)	

31-40	7 (17.5)	0 (0.0)	0.0004 ^s
41-50	3 (7.5)	5 (45.4)	
51-60	1 (2.5)	3 (27.3)	
Gender			
Male (n=31)	23 (57.5)	8 (72.7)	0.188 ^{ns}
Female (n=20)	17 (42.5)	3 (27.3)	
Residence			
Rural (n=39)	30 (75.0)	9 (81.8)	0.293 ^{ns}
Urban (n=12)	10 (25.0)	2 (18.2)	
Clinical features			
Oliguria	29 (72.5)	8 (72.7)	0.178 ^{ns}
Tachycardia	25 (62.5)	7 (63.6)	0.146 ^{ns}
Tachypnea	19 (47.5)	6 (54.5)	0.107 ^{ns}
Hypotension	19 (47.5)	6 (54.5)	0.107 ^{ns}
Anemia	18 (45.0)	4 (36.4)	0.123 ^{ns}
Breathlessness	17 (42.5)	3 (27.3)	0.167 ^{ns}
Sweating	13 (32.5)	3 (27.3)	0.199 ^{ns}
Cyanosis	8 (20.0)	3 (27.3)	0.136 ^{ns}
Hypoxia	8 (20.0)	2 (18.2)	0.148 ^{ns}
Local injury	7 (17.5)	7 (63.6)	0.005 ^s
Disorientation	6 (15.0)	2 (18.2)	0.067 ^{ns}
Jaundice	5 (12.5)	2 (18.2)	0.086 ^{ns}
Miosis	5 (12.5)	0 (0.0)	0.127 ^{ns}
Hypertension	5 (12.5)	0 (0.0)	0.127 ^{ns}
Hematuria	2 (5.0)	4 (36.4)	0.015 ^s
Convulsion	2 (5.0)	0 (0.0)	0.094 ^{ns}
Blister	0 (0.0)	3 (27.3)	0.008 ^s
Bleeding	0 (0.0)	3 (27.3)	0.008 ^s

Note: *p-values were estimated using the Chi-square test; except for age category where Fisher’s exact test was employed; ^s: statistically significant; ^{ns}: statistically non-significant.

A total of 51 patients with AKI were evaluated, including 40 (78.4%) cases due to poisoning and 11 (21.6%) due to envenomation. The age distribution between the two groups displayed a statistically significant difference (p = 0.0004), with envenomation-associated AKI occurring more frequently in older patients, particularly in the 41–60-year age range. There was no significant difference in gender (p = 0.188) or residence (p = 0.293) between the groups. In

addition, most clinical features—including oliguria, tachycardia, tachypnea, hypotension, anemia, breathlessness, and jaundice—were comparable between poisoning- and envenomation-related AKI (all p > 0.05). However, local tissue injury (p = 0.005), hematuria (p = 0.015), blister formation (p = 0.008), and bleeding manifestations (p = 0.008) were significantly more common among envenomation cases. [Table 1]

Table 2: Type and Pattern of Toxic Exposure among the Participants (n=51)

Type of exposure	Agent	Frequency/Percentage (n/%)
Poisoning (n=40)		
	Paraquat	16 (40.0)
	Organophosphates	6 (15.0)
	Rodenticide	3 (7.5)
	Yaba (amphetamine)	2 (5.0)
	Methanol	2 (5.0)
	Copper sulphate	2 (5.0)
	Aluminum phosphide	2 (5.0)
	Unknown	2 (5.0)
	Harpic	1 (2.5)
	Sedatives	1 (2.5)

	Sulphuric acid	1 (2.5)
	Naphthalene	1 (2.5)
	Hair dye	1 (2.5)
Envenomation (n=11)		
	Wasp sting	3 (27.3)
	Snake bite (unknown)	3 (27.3)
	Daboia russelii (Russell’s viper)	3 (27.3)
	Green pit viper	1 (9.1)
	Scorpion sting	1 (9.1)

It is evident that, following toxic exposure, poisoning accounted for the majority (78.4%), while envenomation comprised 21.6% of cases. Paraquat ingestion was the leading cause of poisoning (40%), followed by organophosphate compounds (15%) and rodenticides (7.5%). Other agents such as methanol,

copper sulphate, and aluminum phosphide each contributed to 5% of cases. Among envenomation-related AKI cases, wasp sting, unknown snake bite, and Russell’s viper bite each accounted for 27.3%, while green pit viper and scorpion sting were less frequent (9.1% each). [Table 2]

Table 3: Distribution of Outcomes According to Type of Agent

Type of agent	Resolution (n=24) [n/%]	Chronic kidney disease (n=7) [n/%]	Death (n=18) [n/%]	Total (n=51)
OPC	5 (28)	1 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	6 (11.8)
Paraquat	3 (12.5)	1 (14.3)	10 (71.0)	14 (31.4)
Yaba	1 (4.2)	1 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	2 (3.9)
Methanol	2 (8.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (3.9)
Harpic	1 (4.2)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.0)
Sedative	1 (4.2)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.0)
Sulfuric acid	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (5.6)	1 (2.0)
Rat killer	1 (4.2)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (5.9)
Naphthalene	0 (0.0)	1 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.0)
CuSO ₄	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (11.1)	2 (3.9)
Aluminium Phosphide	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (11.1)	2 (3.9)
Hair dye	1 (4.2)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.0)
Wasp sting	2 (8.3)	1 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	3 (5.9)
Snake bite (unknown)	2 (8.3)	1 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	3 (5.9)
Scorpion	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (5.6)	1 (2.0)
Russell’s viper	0 (0.0)	1 (14.3)	2 (11.1)	3 (5.9)
Green pit viper	1 (4.2)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.0)
Unknown	1 (4.2)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.0)

Note: *OPC = Organophosphate compounds; CuSO₄ = Copper sulphate. Percentages reflect row totals.

Among the 51 patients with toxin-induced AKI, 24 (47.1%) achieved complete renal recovery, 7 (13.7%) progressed to CKD, and 18 (35.3%) died. The distribution of outcomes varied markedly according to the type of toxic exposure. Paraquat poisoning was the most lethal, accounting for 71% of all paraquat cases (10/14) resulting in death, and contributing to over half of all study deaths. Copper sulphate, aluminum phosphide, sulfuric acid ingestion, scorpion sting, and Russell’s viper envenomation were also associated with mortality, though at lower frequencies. In contrast, AKI following OPC ingestion, methanol poisoning, sedative overdose, Harpic ingestion, hair dye exposure, and

wasp stings reported more favorable outcomes, with most patients achieving complete renal recovery. However, OPC and wasp stings contributed a small but notable proportion of CKD cases. Among envenomation cases, Russell’s viper bite was associated with both mortality (11.1%) and CKD development (14.3%). [Table 3]

The overall mortality among patients with toxin-induced AKI was 35.3%. Mortality was slightly higher in the poisoning group (37.5%) compared to the envenomation group (27.3%), though this difference was not statistically significant (p = 0.529). [Figure 1]

Figure 1: Pie Chart Demonstrating the Distribution of Participants Who Died (n=51)

It is clear that, respiratory failure was the leading cause of death, accounting for one-third (33.3%) of all fatalities among patients with acute poisoning and envenomation-related AKI. This was followed by multiorgan dysfunction syndrome (MODS) at 22.2%. In addition, sudden cardiac arrest and disseminated

intravascular coagulation (DIC) each contributed to 16.7% of deaths. Shock was the least common cause, responsible for 11.1% of mortality. [Figure 2]

Figure 2: Bar Chart Illustrating Etiology of Death (n=18)

Note: *MODS: Multiorgan dysfunction syndrome; DIC: Disseminated intravascular coagulation.

Table 4: Hospital Arrival Time According to Mortality, CKD Status, and Overall Outcome in AKI due to Acute Poisoning and Envenomation (n=51)

Outcome category	Hospital arrival (hours) [Mean ± SD]	Range [min-max]	p-value
Mortality			
Death [n=18]	62.89 ± 31.11	20-120	0.001 ^s
Alive [n=33]	41.29 ± 15.35	18-72	
CKD status			
New-onset CKD [n=7]	40.29 ± 13.03	24-60	0.847 ^{ns}
Resolution [n=24]	41.58 ± 16.20	18-72	
Overall outcome			
Poor outcome [n=25]	56.56 ± 28.91	20-120	0.029 ^s
Good outcome [n=24]	41.58 ± 16.20	18-72	

Note: p-values were estimated using unpaired t-tests; ^s: statistical significance; ^{ns}: statistically insignificant.

Patients with poor outcomes and those who died were found to present significantly later to the hospital compared to survivors or patients with complete renal recovery. The mean time to hospital arrival among deceased patients was 62.9 hours, compared to 41.3 hours for survivors (p = 0.001). Similarly, patients with

poor outcomes had a longer median hospital arrival time than those with good outcomes (56.6 vs 41.6 hours; p = 0.029). In contrast, the timing of hospital arrival did not differ significantly between patients who developed new-onset CKD and those who achieved full renal recovery (p = 0.847). [Table 4]

Table 5: Baseline and Peak Creatinine Levels According to Mortality, CKD Status, and Overall Outcome in AKI due to Acute Poisoning and Envenomation (n=51)

Outcome category	Baseline creatinine (mg/dL) [Mean ± SD/range]	p-value	Peak creatinine (mg/dL) [Mean ± SD/range]	p-value
Mortality				
Death [n=18]	6.19 ± 2.37 (3.7–10.3)	0.001 ^s	10.06 ± 2.43 (6–14.2)	0.045 ^s
Alive [n=18]	3.65 ± 2.42 (1.5–13.2)		7.49 ± 4.99 (2–21.9)	
CKD status				
New-onset CKD [n=7]	4.09 ± 2.19 (1.64–7.5)	0.601 ^{ns}	10.39 ± 5.91 (4.4–18.6)	0.075 ^{ns}
Resolution [n=24]	3.54 ± 2.50 (1.5–13.2)		6.64 ± 4.48 (2–21.9)	
Overall outcome				
Poor outcome [n=25]	5.50 ± 2.40 (1.64–10.3)	0.005 ^s	10.15 ± 3.60 (4.4–18.6)	0.001 ^s
Good outcome [n=24]	3.48 ± 2.60 (1.5–13.2)		6.64 ± 4.48 (2–21.9)	

Note: ^s: statistically significant; ^{ns}: non-significant; p-values estimated by unpaired t-tests.

It is visible that, patients who died had markedly elevated baseline (6.19 mg/dL) and peak creatinine levels (10.06 mg/dL) compared with survivors. Both differences were statistically significant. Regarding CKD status, although patients who progressed to new-onset CKD showed higher baseline and peak creatinine values

than those who achieved full resolution, these differences did not reach statistical significance. Lastly, patients categorized as having a poor outcome exhibited significantly higher baseline and peak creatinine levels compared to those with good outcomes. [Table 5]

Table 6: Association of Hypotension and Oliguria with Poor and Good Outcome Groups

Outcomes	Hypotension (MAP<65 mmHg)			Oliguria (<400 ml/day)		
	Present [n/%]	Absent (n=23) [n/%]	p-value	Present (n=26) [n/%]	Absent (n=23) [n/%]	p-value
Good outcome [n=25]	19 (70.4)	6 (22.2)	0.001 ^s	21 (77.8)	4 (14.8)	0.158 ^{ns}
Poor outcome [n=24]	7 (29.2)	17 (70.8)		16 (66.7)	8 (33.3)	

Note: *MAP: mean arterial pressure; ^{ns}: statistically non-significant; ^s: significant; p-value estimated using Chi-squared test.

Nearly three-fourths (70.4%) of patients with a poor outcome experienced hypotension, compared to only 29.2% of those with a good outcome and this difference was statistically significant (p=0.001). On the contrary, oliguria was common in both groups, particularly in the

poor outcome group (77.8% of those patients) and less so in the good outcome group (66.7% of those patients). This difference was not statistically significant (p=0.158). [Table 6]

Table 7: Comparison of Clinical and Laboratory Parameters between Poor and Good Outcome Groups

Characteristics	Poor outcome (n=25)	Good outcome (n=24)	p-value
Haemoglobin (g/dL)			
Mean ± SD	10.51 ± 1.91	11.90 ± 1.96	0.013 ^s
Range [min-max]	6.9-15	8.9-15.9	
Total WBC (cells/mm³)			
Mean ± SD	15783 ± 10748	12354 ± 4104	0.148 ^{ns}
Range [min-max]	1400-53500	6800-21500	
Platelet count (cells/mm³)			
Mean ± SD	153380 ± 91590	203392 ± 49=8928	0.021 ^s
Range [min-max]	9000-405000	58000-280000	
Serum urea (mg/dL)			

Mean ± SD	152.88 ± 54.10	88.88 ± 45.14	0.001 ^s
Range (min-max)	62-245	40-210	
CPK (U/L)			
Mean ± SD	792.6 ± 705.63	392.79 ± 223.78	0.010 ^s
Range (min-max)	175-2725	150-1240	
Serum potassium (mmol/L) [n/%]			
>6.5	11 (40.7)	6 (25.06)	0.162 ^{ns}
<6.5	14 (51.9)	18 (75.0)	
ALT [n/%]			
>2x upper limit	14 (51.9)	0 (0.0)	0.001 ^s
<2x upper limit	11 (40.7)	24 (100.0)	
Prothrombin time [n/%]			
>6 sec above normal	8 (29.6)	5 (20.8)	0.376 ^{ns}
<6 sec above normal	17 (63.0)	19 (79.2)	
WBCT [n/%]			
>20 min	5 (18.5)	3 (12.5)	0.235 ^{ns}
<20 min	0 (0.0)	1 (4.1)	
3-month follow-up [n/%]			
CKD	7 (28.0)	0 (0.0)	0.001 ^s
Normal renal function	0 (0.0)	24 (100.0)	
Death	18 (72.0)	0 (0.0)	

Note: Hemoglobin, WBC, Platelet, serum urea and CPK associations were estimated by independent sample t-tests; serum potassium, ALT, PT, WBCT and 3-month follow up by Chi-squared tests. ^{ns}: statistically non-significant; ^s: significant. CPK: Creatine phosphokinase; ALT: Alanine aminotransferase; WBCT: Whole blood clotting time.

A comparison of clinical and laboratory parameters between the poor-outcome and good-outcome groups revealed several significant differences. Patients with poor outcomes revealed significantly lower hemoglobin and lower platelet counts; they also demonstrated markedly higher serum urea and higher CPK levels. In addition, liver involvement was more prominent among poor-outcome patients, with over half (51.9%) reporting ALT levels more than twice the upper limit of normal, whereas none of the good-outcome patients exhibited such elevation. Electrolyte abnormalities (hyperkalemia), prolonged prothrombin time, and abnormal WBCT did not differ significantly between the groups. At 3-month follow-up, all patients in the good-outcome group had complete renal recovery, while the poor-outcome group exhibited substantial long-term morbidity and mortality, with 28% developing CKD and 72% expiring. [Table 7]

Discussion

In this study, we evaluated the clinical characteristics, biochemical profile, and outcomes of patients with AKI as a consequence of acute poisoning and envenomation.

The predominance of poisoning-related AKI (78.4%) compared with envenomation (21.6%) is in alignment with local epidemiological patterns, where toxic ingestions such as paraquat, organophosphates, and household chemicals remain commonly encountered causes of emergency admissions among young adults [14]. Furthermore, the higher representation of

younger individuals in the poisoning group, contrasted with the older age of envenomation victims, is consistent with prior Indian data reporting that, snakebite and wasp sting-related AKI typically affect rural middle-aged men who are involved in outdoor occupations [15].

Clinical presentation was comparatively similar between the two groups, although envenomation patients displayed significantly more local tissue injury, hematuria, blistering, and bleeding manifestations, features characteristic of hemotoxic and cytotoxic snake venoms common in South Asia, particularly from *Daboia russelii* and *Trimeresurus* species [16]. Moreover, this supports existing regional evidence that, venom-induced coagulopathy and direct nephrotoxicity frequently contribute to AKI through mechanisms such as tubular necrosis, thrombotic microangiopathy, and pigment injury [17].

Furthermore, toxic exposure patterns in our cohort were found similar to regional trends, with paraquat emerging as the leading nephrotoxin. Paraquat poisoning is associated with extremely high fatality rates in Bangladesh due to its easy availability, delayed presentation, and lack of effective antidotes [18]. Besides, the 71% mortality rate observed among paraquat cases in our study is comparable to similar cohorts from Asia, where mortality typically exceeds 60–90% despite aggressive supportive therapy [19]. Additionally, organophosphate poisoning, although common, demonstrated favorable renal outcomes,

reflecting previous literature showing that OPC-related AKI is less frequent and often reversible when managed promptly [20].

On the contrary, envenomation outcomes reported a different pattern. Russell's viper bite was associated with both mortality and progression to CKD, consistent with a paper from Myanmar documenting that Russell's viper envenomation frequently leads to severe AKI, thrombotic microangiopathy, and permanent renal sequelae despite antivenom availability [21]. Besides, wasp stings also contributed to CKD in our cohort, supporting earlier South Asian reports suggesting rhabdomyolysis and pigment nephropathy as key mechanisms leading to persistent renal injury [22].

The overall mortality rate of 35.3% in our cohort is substantial, though comparable to Indian reports on toxin-induced AKI, where mortality ranged from 20–45% depending on toxin severity and access to timely dialysis [3, 23].

We found that, respiratory failure, primarily driven by paraquat-induced pulmonary fibrosis and OP-induced respiratory paralysis, was the leading cause of death, followed by MODS and DIC. These findings reinforce the multisystemic nature of toxin-mediated AKI and the need for rapid organ support.

A significant contribution of this study is the demonstration of renal biochemical predictors of outcome. Higher baseline and peak creatinine levels were strongly associated with mortality and poor outcomes, consistent with international evidence linking creatinine trajectory to AKI severity and survival [24]. Although patients who progressed to CKD demonstrated numerically higher creatinine levels at presentation, this difference did not reach significance, likely due to small sample size.

Additionally, the comparison of clinical and laboratory parameters between good and poor outcome groups highlighted the significance of multi-organ involvement. Anemia and thrombocytopenia were significantly associated with poor outcomes, consistent with South Asian studies identifying hematological abnormalities as markers of severe envenomation or systemic toxicity [25]. Furthermore, elevated serum urea and markedly higher CPK levels were additional predictors of poor prognosis, stressing the role of dehydration, muscle breakdown, and rhabdomyolysis in toxin-induced renal injury [26]. Liver dysfunction (ALT >2× ULN) was observed exclusively in poor-outcome patients, supporting reports of hepatotoxicity in paraquat, OP compounds, and viper envenomation [27].

The long-term renal outcomes were concerning: 13.7% progressed to CKD, similar to previously published papers reporting CKD progression in 10–20% of toxin-associated AKI cases [28]. Permanent renal sequelae result from cortical necrosis, glomerular injury, or

prolonged ischemic insult; mechanisms well established in paraquat ingestion and viper envenomation [29].

The findings reveal that 70.4% of patients with a poor outcome experienced hypotension, a stark contrast to only 29.2% of those with a good outcome. This difference was statistically significant ($p=0.001$), suggesting hypotension is a critical risk factor. In contrast, while oliguria was frequent in both groups (77.8% in the poor outcome group vs. 66.7% in the good outcome group), the difference was not considered statistically significant ($p=0.158$). This indicates a weaker or absent causal link between oliguria alone and the patient outcome as defined in this specific study.

Lastly, delayed hospital presentation was significantly associated with higher mortality and poor outcomes in AKI following poisoning and envenomation. Early intervention remains crucial, as timely resuscitation and supportive care can mitigate progression to severe renal injury and reduce fatality, consistent with findings from regional studies [3].

Overall, the findings of this study reinforce the urgent public health need for improved regulation of highly nephrotoxic agents such as paraquat, community education on safe pesticide handling, early referral systems for envenomation and strengthened rural emergency care infrastructure. In addition, early recognition of biochemical predictors, such as rising creatinine, hyper-CPK, and elevated liver enzymes, can aid clinicians in identifying high-risk patients who require intensive monitoring and early dialysis support.

Limitations

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged. First, the sample size was relatively small ($n=51$), which may have limited the statistical power to detect subtle associations, particularly regarding CKD progression and rare toxic exposures. Second, the study was conducted in a single tertiary care hospital, which may introduce referral bias and limit generalizability to rural or primary care settings. Third, long-term follow-up was limited to only three months, so late-onset CKD or delayed recovery could not be fully captured. Finally, specific biochemical and imaging markers of renal injury, such as urinary biomarkers or renal ultrasonography, were not systematically assessed, which may have provided additional prognostic information.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Acute poisoning and envenomation are significant contributors to AKI, with paraquat ingestion and Russell's viper envenomation carrying the highest risk of mortality and CKD progression. Overall mortality was high, with respiratory failure and multiorgan dysfunction as the leading causes of death. Moreover, late arrival to hospital, elevated baseline and peak

creatinine levels, anemia, thrombocytopenia, elevated serum urea and CPK, and liver enzyme derangement were strong predictors of poor outcomes.

Public education programs such as community-level programs on the dangers of chemical exposures, safe handling of pesticides, and prompt medical attention for snakebites and other envenomation are essential. In addition, strengthening policies on the sale, storage, and use of highly toxic pesticides and chemicals are recommended. Finally, establishing a regional registry of toxin-induced AKI cases could improve understanding of epidemiology, outcomes, and preventive strategies in Bangladesh and surrounding regions.

Conflict of Interest

The authors disclose no conflict of interest.

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